

Interstanding the industrial district: contrasting conceptual images as a road to insight

Bengt Johannisson, Leonardo Centeno Caffarena, Allan Fernando Discua Cruz, Mircea Epure, Esther Hormiga Pérez, Magdalena Kapelko, Karen Murdock, Douglas Nanka-Bruce, Martina Olejárová, Alizabeth Sanchez Lopez, Antti Sekki, Maria-Cristina Stoian, Henrik Tötterman & Angelo Bisignano

In this paper we offer an approach to learning about the unique features of industrial districts as a socio-economic phenomenon that is based on differences. Instead of searching for one generic theory that may explain the unique construction of an industrial district or one universal way of getting under the skin of its subjects we propose ‘interstanding’ as a road to insight. The title alludes to different relationships: between theoretical frameworks and empirical approaches, between writing and reflecting on the one hand, creating conversations, talking and listening on the other, between teacher and student, between the academic and business communities. In the paper this ‘interstanding’ perspective of knowledging is demonstrated in the context of an annual international doctoral course on SMEs in economic and regional development. The participating doctoral students are organized into research teams, each furnished with a specific theoretical perspective on localized economic development, and subsequently jointly brought to the industrial district of Gnosjö in Sweden in order to meet with owner-managers and further local stakeholders. The student groups report on their field experiences, thereby creating maps as diverse as the different theoretical frameworks being used. These contrasting images of the district’s generic features and sustainability are used as an input to a conclusive polylogue seminar that offers an ‘interstanding’ that, on the one hand, reminds the participants that any, including scientifically investigated, reality is socially constructed, and, on the other, communicates that tensions between alternative conceptual constructs, especially if substantiated in empirical research, offer an inspiring road to knowledge.

Keywords: industrial district; methodology; interstanding; crystallization; education; Gnosjö

1. The challenge

In the same way as any economic activity is socially embedded, every social-science enquiry is as much a political game as a search for insight. It is true, not all social researchers are explicitly involved in feeding findings into policy-making or taking a public stand on contemporary ethical issues. Nevertheless, the choices being made in the research process signal a positioning as regards favoured paradigm, preferred theory and favourite methodology, certainly rooted in personal and collective values. This in turn implies taking a stand in the ongoing debate on appropriate ways of relating to and studying social phenomena. The very meaning of academia as a collective with its own practices is to encourage interaction and dialogue so that those who have to speak out on critical issues in the research process get the support needed. Academia in this respect appears as a meta-community of practice (Wenger 1998), since it should encourage alternative approaches to scientific enquiry. The (inter)national academic context, the discipline concerned and the individual university in question all contribute to the rules of the game that the individual researcher plays. The new generation of academics has to be carefully socialized into this constantly emerging institutional setting.

In the context of the European Doctoral Programme in Entrepreneurship and Small Business Management, jointly run by the Autonomous University of Barcelona, Spain, and Växjö University, Sweden, educating for academic professionalism is not only brought up as part of the general discourse on academic enquiry in the classroom. Experiential and social learning (e.g. by way of role modelling and peer teaching/exchange) is important also in the academic setting. Accordingly, the programme course 'SMEs in Economic and Regional Development (SMERD)' has for 15 years been staged as an intellectual challenge beyond traditional classroom teaching. As we will elaborate further below, the students on this course are expected to appropriate different theoretical views and enact them in empirical research. In groups/teams the students advocate the chosen conceptual framing and associated field experience at the same time as they question the results of the peer groups.

To our mind there are three generic barriers to a deeper insight into complex socio-economic phenomena. The first is the belief that proposed features of complex phenomena can be generalized across similar, let alone different, socio-cultural settings. A second limiting assumption is that access to such insight is independent of both the one(s) who conduct(s) the (re)search and the adopted methodology. A third obstacle is that the university context as an arena for knowledge creation and learning is far from an ideal setting for dialogue. The teacher 'overstands' the students with respect to supposedly relevant knowledge as much as researchers using an objectivist approach and associated ostensive definitions 'overstand' the subjects concerned in field research. 'Understanding' in social research is, in contrast, associated with an emic view where the researcher submits to the worldview of the subjects, their performative definitions and local knowledge. The researcher then

runs the risk of ‘going native’, that is to unreflectively take field experiences for granted. Only an experienced researcher can withstand such temptations and instead critically use her/his own experience to practice reflexivity (Alvesson and Skoldberg 2000). Consequently, interpretative approaches aiming at ‘understanding’ (sense-making) mean that the (senior) researcher in practice overstands both the subjects and the students who by definition are inexperienced researchers.

Researchers, though, are as much as anyone else members of multiple communities of practice, from the everyday family setting to the professional academic world. Being an experienced researcher not only means having a privileged knowledge position but also being dependent on existing mental maps. In this perspective junior researchers have a generic advantage when exploring new images of ‘reality’. Their inexperience not only means knowledge that has not yet matured into insight but also less prejudice and more playfulness, that is a creative potential for coping with the unexpected. We propose the notion of ‘interstanding’ for depicting the staging, involvement and outcome of conversations where scientific enquiry and inter(active) learning combine across established boundaries. Our argument is that it is the very interrelating of different conceptual perspectives as applied to empirical phenomena that provides further insights. Here interstanding thus means that students are invited to a practice where they stay learners while becoming researchers, and vice versa, that educators acknowledge the need for continuous learning.¹

In the context of entrepreneurship and small business as a spatial phenomenon the industrial district, in other words, a localized cluster of (small) manufacturing firms in one or two sectors that is historically, culturally and institutionally embedded, invites further research. The crucial characteristic of an industrial district is its *organizing* including features such as (1) a willingness to *co-operate* between the firms; (2) the existence of *strong networks* of small firms; (3) *competition on a range of dimensions* and not just on price; (4) the *work force*, and (5) *trust and co-operation* within the industrial district itself (Pyke and Sengenberger 1992: 4–5). There has been substantial research concerning industrial districts since its origins with the works of Alfred Marshall (1920 [1890]), energized by the seminal report by Piore and Sabel (1984). There is no space here for a review of this literature, which means that we confine ourselves to a few comments. The interested reader will find many papers in the field already in previous issues of this journal. As pointed out by Martin and Sunley (2003), more focused research on localized clusters in general and industrial districts in particular as well as a number of intriguing issues are too easily absorbed by unreflected research and opportunistic applications by policy-makers.

Recently the viability of the classic industrial district has been questioned, due to the entry of, first, low-cost countries such as the Baltic countries and then of China on the world market. Nevertheless, the belief in spatially clustered economic activity remains, but so does the need for further enquiries into the phenomenon. As a point of departure for the present discourse industrial districts are considered to materialize collective entrepreneurship, in other words, they are considered to ‘consist of internally well-integrated, yet independent, businesses which collectively

demonstrate great potential for self-organizing' (Johannisson 2000a: 289, compare also Johannisson 2003). This contrasts with other views, e.g. the notion of 'collective efficiency' (Schmitz 1995) and the general idea of creating competitiveness, cf., for example, Porter (1990). Using metaphorical language many have pointed out the complex relationships between the many actors, the intended use of arranged agreements and the impact of collaboration on the making of a region (Maskell *et al.* 1998, Mackinnon *et al.* 2004). More reflected empirical research includes quantitative as well as qualitative research. As regards quantitative research, Johannisson at an early stage did network/graph analyses of localized interpersonal relations in the Gnosjö industrial district and neighbouring localities (compare, for example, Johannisson 1983, Johannisson *et al.* 1994). Later, for example, Giuliani (2007) has also applied graph analysis to localized clusters. While the latter author adopts a rationalistic view

Figure 1. Academic quality as a three-dimensional criterion.

of firm behaviour in clusters, Johannisson and others recognize the irrationalities of existentially driven small family businesses tied to place.

Complex socio-cultural phenomena such as industrial districts obviously lend themselves to qualitative research. Accordingly, 'interstanding' is not the only road to insight into industrial districts that aims at recognizing their idiosyncrasies. Sometimes researchers acquire knowledge over a long time that integrates articulated/scientific and tacit/intuitive knowledge (Beccattini 1990). This means that the researcher epitomizes the bridge between academic scholarship and practical expertise, a special kind of interstanding indeed. Interpretative narrative approaches aiming at genuine 'understanding', making the researcher a humble listener and observer, are much needed as well. Wigren (2003), however, has done ethnographic fieldwork in the Gnosjö industrial district in Sweden. With Johannisson she combines the lessons from one-year close-up studies with three decades of repeated research in the region (Johannisson and Wigren 2006). As indicated, researchers far too often refer to singular conceptual approaches to capture the privileged position of 'overstanding' others. This stance refers as much to the main bulk of analytical enquiries into industrial districts as to critical discursive approaches such as the one applied by Pettersson (2004).²

The argumentation above underlines the general need for openness and humbleness in the university context. Figure 1, accordingly, proposes that quality in academic work should be associated with the very interrelationships

between research, education and community dialogue. This suggests, for example, that academic education, however advanced as regards pedagogical methods it may be, lacks quality if it is not based on writings at the research frontier. Wherever possible, knowledge-creation should involve not just (academic) research but also invite students and practitioners to a ‘trialogue’. Research itself then appears as a learning process to everyone involved, the researchers/teachers themselves as well as the practitioners encountered in the field. The notion of Triple Helix (Etzkowitz and Leydesdorff 1997) has made evident that university involvement in regional development may benefit both researchers and students. On the one hand, the junior researchers/doctoral students appear as ‘tourists’ in the industrial district (cf. Johannisson and Wigren 2006); on the other, their alien status makes them become affected in a way not anticipated when encountering the empirical field. If guided by different metaphors/theories, these unprejudiced experiences promise clear-cut images of the empirical world being visited.

In the next section we present the above-mentioned doctoral course as conceptually embedded field research and the ‘interstanding’ approach as a means for uncovering the collective entrepreneurship associated with a localized business community as it appears in the Gnosjo industrial district in Sweden. We will then focus on the research-education relationship according to figure 1. Section 3 presents the different conceptual lenses that have been used to provide alternative images of the dynamics of the industrial-district phenomenon. In Section 4 we reflect upon the theoretical and methodological lessons for senior/ junior researchers as enquiring visitors to a local setting. The concluding section discusses what further research the learning exercise may trigger as substantive lessons for practitioners within and outside the industrial district concerned. In addition, a ‘visiting doctoral student’ – Angelo Bisignano – participating in the educational events with a Researcher Mobility scholarship (REM) from the Gate2Growth Academic Network, provides some meta-reflexions on the overall (ad)venture.

2. Practising the interstanding approach–beyond triangulation and crystallization

Objectivist approaches to social enquiry aim at identifying the general laws that supposedly organize socio-economic phenomena. Constructionist approaches strive to make the appearance of phenomena in their local context intelligible, which calls for a dialogue, or rather polylogue, between those involved. While the former approach is pretentious with regard to its outcome and universal claims, the constructionist approach is pompous with respect to the elevation of the researcher to an omnipotent initiator of knowledging processes. The way to avoid both the Scylla of the objectivist approach and the Charybdis of a constructionist stance proposed here is to state the relativity of any a priori conceptual framework, provide optional frameworks and use the tensions between them as strongholds for interpretative endeavours.

Morgan (1980) associates choices in studies with paradigms, metaphors (theories) and puzzle-solving (methodology). This view is announced in his own seminal work on alternative approaches in social-science studies (Burrell and Morgan 1988 [1979]) and elaborated on in his equally influential study of optional images of organization (Morgan 2006). On the theoretical level, Allison (1971) in his famous study of the Cuban missile crisis in the 1960s illustrates the power of combining different frameworks. In the field of entrepreneurship and small business Johansson (1999) practises three different paradigmatic perspectives –an analytical-normative, a narrative and a Foucaultian one –to make sense out of the relations between owner-managers and consultants. Eisenhardt (1989) is even bolder, arguing that the use of multiple ways of bridging between the conceptual frameworks and empirical worlds will provide a more accurate image of reality, a more conclusive grounded theory, than analytically generated models.

While few individual researchers bring in alternative paradigms or metaphors/theories, many of them adopt multiple methodologies. Jick (1979) argues that insights gained from adopting different methodologies can be amalgamated, ‘triangulated’, to a singular richer image of the phenomenon. Practising ‘case survey analysis’, Larsson (1993), too, holds up the combination of nomothetic and idiographic methodologies. Since the aim is to substantiate generalizations, his way of organizing data, as much as Jick’s, though, submits to the basic logic of the objectivist approach. Methodological triangulation, however, is not the only way of creating diversity in a (qualitative) research setting. Quoting Denzin (1978), Janesick (2000) points out that triangulation may encompass multiple theories and investigators as well as methodologies and data sources, according to Jick (1979) and Yin (1994), respectively.

Janesick (2000), as well as Richardson (1994), argue that the triangulation metaphor is inappropriate in qualitative research, especially as adopted within a postmodern view. Richardson instead proposes the notion of ‘crystallization’ to point out that there are many ways of interpreting the social world. The crystal combines ‘symmetry and substance with an infinite variety of shapes, substances, transmutations, multidimensionalities, and angles of approach (Richardson 1994: 522). Expanding on this metaphor, Janesick (2000: 392) suggests that including different disciplines, including also non-academic activities such as journal writing in the design of a study is a mode of practising crystallization. While the notion of crystallization thus announces quite an ambitious approach, the very setting of the Vaxjo doctoral course and associated field research invites crystallization as an all-embracing metaphor. The wide differences as regards cultural background and professional training of the participants offered a basic generic variety of views and insights. These were organized by the course manager/senior researcher/author who himself had the local knowledge needed to supplement and support the students, compare also Johannisson and Wigren (2006).

The systematic way of creating contrasts and staging a polylogue, in the field as well as in the classroom, makes the course design add further dynamism to the

original ideas behind crystallization. The cultural and biographical embedding of students/junior researchers make them sense and become affected by different aspects of the phenomenon being studied. Different socio-cultural origins of the members on a research team will thus amplify the variety of interpretations that can be generated out of (multiple) data sources. The kaleidoscope is an appropriate metaphor to catch this variety and dynamics.³ By changing the theory/conceptual metaphor new ‘self-evident’ images of reality (the industrial district) present themselves in the same way as turning the kaleidoscope constructs new patterns of coloured glass pieces. The conclusive outcome of the crystallization approach will thus not be an ultimate ‘holistic’ image of the phenomenon concerned but rather a richer understanding characterized by ‘disciplined variety’, which invites the reader’s own interpretations, opening up for either further academic enquiry or offering inspiration for reflective practitioners.

Anti-positivistic research into entrepreneurship, led by European researchers (see, for example, Hjorth and Steyaert 2004) promises new insights. Nevertheless, objectivist approaches still dominate doctoral-thesis work in most national settings. It is important that postgraduate students do not lose their intellectual foothold and legitimacy in their own national academic setting when they are invited to an international educational context where they are challenged by new learning experiences. Multiple conceptual frameworks and associated optional ways of collecting/creating data may, however, offer a feasible way of helping the students to break away from single-framework objectivist approaches. By organizing the participants in postgraduate courses into teams which are equipped with contrasting conceptual glasses, uniformity is kept within the group while conceptual variety is created across teams. The Yin (1994) case methodology is then appropriate since, on the one hand, it submits to the objectivist approach and advises a preferred theory and, on the other, tempts rival theoretical frameworks to prove themselves in the same empirical context. The Yin apparatus also arranges different data collection techniques into an agenda that is feasible to carry out during the limited time (a month in our case) of an academic (doctoral) course.

Table 1. The institutional repertoire for human exchanges in society.

<i>Interaction rationales</i>			
<i>Forms of interaction</i>	<i>Calculative</i>	<i>Ideational</i>	<i>Genuine</i>
Hierarchical	Corporation	Association	Clan
Network type	Market	(Social) Movement	Circle

Sources: Sjöstrand 1992: 1028.

The setting for the combined learning/theorizing venture on the interface between research and education in the model in figure 1 is thus the European Doctoral Programme in Entrepreneurship and Small Business Development. In

2005 the 12 doctoral students were organized into four student teams and these groups with three members each were equipped with different conceptual glasses. The Sjöstrand (1992) notion of 'institution' was used to systematically identify alternative ways of conceptualizing the industrial district as a socio-economic phenomenon. Sjöstrand's original set of six institutions, according to table 1, was reduced to four by merging the two rationales 'ideational' and 'genuine' into one 'social' rationale, thus providing four 'ideal' institutions, as presented in table 2.

The intellectual input to the doctoral course that provided the learning setting for the venture included a number of lectures given by both local and visiting researchers on the different spatial images of localized business activity. Additional classes informed the students about the history and industry of the Gnosjö industrial district, where the field research was going to take place. With the senior first-mentioned co-author of this paper as course organizer the students were given an assignment which read as follows (slightly edited):⁴

A significant part of the course contents unit, and an even bigger share of its examination, concerns comparative field research in the Gnosjö industrial district. The empirical part of this project is *embedded in reflection*: before, during and after the site visits. Your reflexivity should include both the inquiry as a process and its outcome as the structuring of a perceived reality originating in encounters with representatives of firms and organizations/institutions. The point of departure is, in addition to the already presented literature associated with the course, *different distinct perspectives* which will be allocated among four groups, each including three students. The conceptual point of departure is the 'raw' and 'processed' course literature as it appears in the reports, according to previous assignments. Four papers provide additional compulsory input. Two of these papers will be read by all groups – 'On the rationale behind "irrational" institutions' by Sven-Erik Sjöstrand (1992) and 'A macro-view of the Gnosjö entrepreneurial spirit' by Charlie Karlsson and Jan Larsson (1993). The two other papers are specific for each group as elaborated below.

According to this assignment, each one of the groups is expected to *advocate* its conceptual framework for understanding the Gnosjö industrial district and for judging its viability on a competitive international market. This means that the *different conceptual frameworks* represent mutually rival theories. The generic framework proposed by Sjöstrand which structures different *institutions* as 'a kind of infrastructure that facilitates (or hinders) human coordination and (re)allocation of resources' (1992: 1011) can be used to order the proposed alternative frameworks.

The focused unit of analysis is thus the industrial district, in our case the Gnosjö industrial district. Each group is expected to experience and report it through the lens provided by the allocated conceptual framework/institution as reflected in the assigned literature (for the student groups to complete on their own initiative). Group 1 is, for instance, expected to approach the industrial district as if it were a 'corporation'. Your main data source, although not the only one, will be interviews with entrepreneurs and other local stakeholders (in 2005 the mayor in one of the municipalities constituting the Gnosjö industrial district, (blue-collar) trade union representatives and the CEO of the local Industrial Development Centre). The general conceptual input to the project is thus the course literature which has already been presented. With the additional help of the papers that elaborate on the course literature, each group is to provide a 'special' image of the industrial district being researched. The presentation of this image will aim at demonstrating the relevance of that particular framework for understanding the structuring of business activity with respect to contents (what?) and process (how?).

With respect to contents the use of design, family business succession and international challenges should be taken into special consideration. As far as process is concerned, personal as well as

interorganizational relationships and contemporary economic and social changes in the industrial district should be paid special attention to.

Table 2. Optional ways of conceptualizing the industrial-district phenomenon.

<i>Interaction rationales</i>		<i>Calculative</i>	<i>Social (Ideational/genuine)</i>
Form of interaction	Hierarchy	'Corporation'	'Federation'
	Network	'Industrial Market/ Technology System'	Networked Community'

Following the Yin (1994) agenda, the four student teams prepared different sets of questions, according to the allocated theoretical framework. It was up to each team to do both further homework (e.g. consulting additional literature, visiting the firms' and the municipality's websites and contacting institutions in the region) and organize their work on site during the fieldwork (e.g. allocating the questions between team members, taking turns at taking notes, watching the body language of the practitioners and reflecting upon the physical setting). The students were reminded that they had to compete for the informant's attention during each visit, which lasted for about one and a half hours.

The two-day field trip to the Gnosjö industrial district, about an hour's drive by car from Växjö (University) was carried out in April 2005. Guided by teachers who had themselves done research in the region (one day by the senior author of this paper) the students not only met with (five) (owner) managers but also with the mayor in one of the municipalities in the region, blue-collar trade-union representatives and the CEO of the Industrial Development Centre. The overall evaluation of the field assignment included their performance in the field, individually and as synchronized team members. The role of the accompanying teacher was that of facilitator. Once the students were introduced they were left to use their initiatives.

The course design thus reflects a decentralized structure where the student teams operated independently as regards both conceptual elaboration and modelling within the frames given by the assignment and the associated field research. These rules of the game are reflected in the texts in Subsections 3.2–3.5, which summarize the substantive contents of the reports submitted by each student team. Each group has made its own interpretation of both the directives as regards conceptual approach and the way to approach the interlocutors in their empirical setting. Again we want to underline that the reader should not expect a comprehensive review of the literature in each conceptual domain but rather see the co-existence of different conceptual lenses and associated empirical findings as the very point of the reading experience.

As an integrated part of the course design and examination the students presented their conclusive written reports on their enquiry into the industrial district in an interactive seminar at the university. In an atmosphere of rivalry each team was then expected to eagerly advocate their own (theoretical) view, using their field

experiences as confirming evidence. The rival teams, each promoting a different but equally firm belief, were thus encouraged to intensively question the view of the reporting group. Revolving the kaleidoscope, the examination thus turned into a drama, which was directed by the first author/teacher, occasionally supplemented with other teacher(s) involved in the course. The evaluation of the students not only paid attention to the quality of the written group reports but also to the performance in the seminar of the individual and the whole team, including the role-playing within the group, the intensity and integration of team members in the joint presentation and their collective ability to assert their own arguments when contradicted by members of the other teams. The overall grading of the course, which also included individual literature assignments, followed that of the field research.

The multiple dialogues or ‘polylogue’ produced what we here address as an ‘interstanding’ of the industrial-district phenomenon. Unexpected new insights into the industrial-district phenomenon emerged through the very contrasting of different (conceptual) views. These insights come to life at the interface between the ‘overstanding’ etic view created by contrasting conceptual approaches and the ‘understanding’ emic perspective that the field research with its openness and deference to local and immediate impressions represents. The quality of the staged ‘polylogue’ in terms of providing new knowledge as an outcome of ‘interstanding’ originates in structural features of the set-up as well as in the learning process itself. As indicated, many of the 2005 students originated in developing-country/reformed- Europe contexts with a limited experience in research methodology but with different cultural and professional backgrounds and all with a trained capacity to be sensitive to alternative values and norms. When the student research teams were built, the students’ gender, age, cultural origin, educational background and personal experience as well as their proficiency in the English language, social skills and personal interests in the subject/conceptual approach were considered in order to guarantee variety. While less experienced students were given the opportunity to elaborate on a favoured conceptual framework, those with outspoken firm beliefs were deliberately ‘forced’ to join a team that was directed to adopt a contrasting conceptual view. The general ambition was to create a context that could offer both individual and collective learning experiences.

Reflecting upon their lessons in a one-year perspective (April 2006), the doctoral students/junior authors refer to the field-research assignment as an adventure, as both an intellectual and an emotional experience. The experimental learning they experienced was not just an outcome of the bridging of the phases of the enactment of the assignment: planning (using the conceptual framework to generate a model to subsequently become operationalized), the field visit itself and the written and oral conclusive reporting. The enactment of the assignment also meant building a team and negotiating a conceptual framework with people with little experience of group work and with contrasting basic theoretical views, cultural backgrounds and/or personalities. The learning process was compressed and dramatic. During the first day in the field the students were inactive, playing a waiting game, whereas the second day they fought intensely for the informants’ attention. The ‘moment of truth’,

the reporting at the conclusive seminar, turned into a very dramatic event, where each group, referring to ‘their model’ and associated confirming field research, confidently and aggressively claimed ownership of the ultimate truth about the Gnosjö industrial district. According to the participants, the rivalry between contrasting theoretical frameworks, which Yin (1994) presents as an analytical exercise, turned into passionate and joyful competition. The win-win game taught in a stimulating way what an understanding of the world individual theories can communicate and what they leave out.

3. Alternative images of an industrial district

3.1 The Gnosjö industrial district – an introduction

The Gnosjö region, which is recognized as the only industrial district in Sweden, accommodates (2006) about 80 000 people and 1500 industrial firms. The region is located in the southern part of the country and its success story goes several centuries back. The active business community was originally carried by the ability to use water power to stretch metal wire into the production of quite simple consumer products. After World War II a plastic industry emerged that utilized the same concept of making simple objects at low prices for both consumer and producer markets. Cost-efficiency (Karlsson and Larsson 1993) and dense social embedding (Johannisson 1983, Johannisson *et al.* 1994, Johannisson 2000a) made the collective business community and the region very successful. However, at the turn of the millennium increasing globalization meant challenges that for the first time have shaken the region to its foundations (Johannisson and Wigren 2006). Even if the business community at large is certainly internationalized (Johannisson *et al.* 1994), outsourcing to the Baltic countries starting early, it has taken the small firms quite some time to find ways to deal with the challenges caused by the big Far East countries.

The need for more designed products is a global challenge to all businesses, although amplified in the Gnosjö region because of its small-firm structure and strong traditions in subcontracting. Increased need for design is one of the main concerns of the local Industrial Development Centre (IDC). Bringing in a new generation into the family businesses which dominate the region appears as one feasible way to open up for more focus on design. This suggests that a problem may be turned into a solution. Succession issues are certainly on the agenda in many firms – before 2015 more than 500 of the owner-managers in the Gnosjö region are expected to retire. Of course these future prospects create an urgent need for competent successors. The Swedish regulatory framework represents the macro side of this challenge, while the way the family deals with the succession reflects the micro perspective (Bjuggren and Sund 2002: 125). The inside successor is in a unique position to, on the one hand, acquire her/his ‘family idiosyncratic knowledge’ by observing and listening, on the other to learn about, for example, design by way of education. However, having accustomed themselves to other ways of life, many of the potential successors in the

Gnosjö-region are not interested in taking over the family's business (Johannisson and Wigren 2006). These brief accounts of the particulars of the Gnosjö-industrial district reflected in the group assignment, probably suffice to qualify the region as a very complex and dynamic socio-economic phenomenon, which invites different kinds of interpretations. Next we elaborate somewhat on the four alternative conceptual frameworks proposed in table 2, thereby demonstrating that they highlight different aspects of the region and its business community.

3.2 *The industrial district as a corporation*

3.2.1 *Conceptual overview*

Combining a calculative rationale with asymmetrical (power) or hierarchical relationships, the corporation governs exchange by way of information located in prices and other market signals. This perspective invites the transaction cost theory, which states that these costs determine whether corporate structures or the market-organized economic activity will be relevant (Williamson 1979). Hence, the existence of the firms depends on the outcome of the struggle for efficiency (Nooteboom 1993). According to Coase (1937) and Williamson (1975), markets and hierarchy are the two main governance modes. The choice between the two depends on the transaction costs encountered. When transaction costs exceed the benefits of outside production, then production in the 'hierarchical' structure of the firm is preferred. Williamson (1979) further extended this differentiation by introducing a third governance structure between market and hierarchy called 'hybrid', which are individual contracts between parties, creating a joint surplus through co-operation (Blomqvist *et al.* 2002).

Williamson (1975, 1985) expressed the following reasons that give rise to transaction costs: (1) *bounded rationality* (people have limited memories and limited cognitive processing power); (2) *opportunism* (self-interest-seeking with guile); (3) *uncertainty*; and (4) *transaction specificity of assets*. These features generally disfavour small firms because of the threshold cost of transactions (including the cost of setting up and executing an appointment with a potential transaction partner, the cost of making or judging an offer or the cost of setting up a contract). This is a cost incurred regardless of the size of the transaction, so that, although each transaction is smaller, it weighs more heavily on a small firm. Moreover, small firms are less rational, more sensitive to uncertainty and more vulnerable to opportunism. Owing to relatively low levels of education and training among the business owner and his/her staff, small firms also have less capacity for absorbing external information. Additionally, the perspective from which small firms perform external scanning is often dominated (and limited) by the personal perspective of the entrepreneur (Nooteboom 1993).

In the industrial district co-operative physical and social proximity will enhance relationships (Pyke and Sengenberger 1992, Rabellotti 1997). Firms located in particular places benefit from the specific qualities that render them a competitive

advantage, addressed as ‘localized capabilities’ (Maskell *et al.* 1998). Such regional advantages, which are built through historical processes, according to Maskell *et al.* (1998) have four main elements: the institutional endowment, the built structures, the natural resources and the localized knowledge and skills. Increased internationalization often transforms formerly critically important characteristics of production or other localized capabilities into ‘ubiquities’, implying that localized capabilities are being destroyed and no longer provide a competitive edge.

As elaborated on in figure 2, transaction costs supposedly exert a very strong influence on the competitiveness of the kind of localized small-firm network that the Gnosjö business community represents. Large and powerful external customers dictate prices, the calculative rationale among firms. The price issue is the focal point of other challenges such as those emanating from the need for increased internationalization that these firms face.

Figure 2. Modelling the industrial district in a transaction-cost framework.

3.2.2 Lessons from the field

Practising a low-cost strategy, the firms in the district still operate as subcontractors to large Swedish manufacturers such as Volvo and Scania (both truck manufacturers) and Ericsson (telecommunications). Over the last five or ten years, however, it has become far more difficult to continue to provide these items at the increasingly lower prices that customers demand. A third generation family business that we encountered, for example, has seen prices for its product decline by 35% over the past decade. Its inability to keep up with the increasingly harsh international competition will make the company lose its biggest, as well as one of its oldest, customers. The CEO states ‘I almost had to tell them to go to hell with the price they were offering’. Many other companies face similar challenges.

Some local firms, especially the larger ones, deal with the cost pressure by outsourcing. The third-generation family business mentioned above has created production facilities in the neighbouring country of Lithuania. The business leader even considers moving the whole production to this Baltic country and concentrating on marketing in Sweden. Two other companies visited have outsourced production capacity to China and Taiwan.

Encounters with business leaders thus confirm that quality and price rather than trust govern business relationships. The management in one of the largest firms stated that the days of relational contracting with local suppliers are now counted. The CEO at the IDC argues that there is a need for more formal co-operation among the local firms. These are, however, often reluctant and suspicious of participating in such structures. This unwillingness to collaborate formally is due to many factors including

(1) the eroding trust between the different firms, making them suspicious of each other's intention, fearing that some may behave opportunistically, and (2) the bounded rationality of the principals in the firms, which prevents them from seeing the potential benefits in such an action. Some have, however, realized the potential benefits from collaboration in areas such as marketing and the purchasing of raw materials. The third-generation owner-manager giving voice above suggests that the local trade association should be used for the joint purchasing of raw materials (such as electricity), a rational way of reducing costs.

Figure 3. The Industrial district as a technology system.

3.3 *The industrial district as an industrial market/technology system*

3.3.1 *Conceptual overview*

According to Teece (2000), the growth of the (global) knowledge economy can be explained by characteristics such as the rapid and cost-effective exchange of information, the expansion of markets for different types of products, the deregulation of product and labour markets and the increased flow of financial assets around the world. Therefore a country and region cannot compete on costs alone but must rather focus on high value-added goods and services that cannot easily be transferred. The improvements that result from new knowledge will not only sediment in the routines and procedures of the firms but also in the locality as a networked system.

The received view in management is that products should be developed within companies and subsequently be introduced on the market. However, many researchers (Håkansson 1987, Raffa 1992) stress that the process and product technology have become so complex today that technical exchange between different actors (i.e. individuals and firms) on the market is needed. Figure 3 presents the challenges of the Gnosjö industrial district in this perspective.

The two 'steps' indicated in the figure suggests that the two major challenges that the Gnosjö business community faces are to be approached sequentially. First, the problem with ageing owner-managers has to be dealt with by searching for successors inside the family/the firm or recruiting them externally (Step 1). When this challenge has been taken care of within the existing technological regime, the need for a more knowledge-intensive broader orientation of activities has to be met, including for example design (Step 2).

With the help of Carlsson and Stankiewicz (1991) the general image of the industrial district as a networked market can be qualified as a technology system. This may be mapped as a dynamic network of agents interacting in a specific industrial field regulated by a particular institutional infrastructure that supports the generation, diffusion, and utilization of technology. Networking is particularly important for innovativeness because of the uncertain process of searching, selecting and satisfying customers. Co-operation with other actors is called for since the environment is basically unknowable. The way markets are organized frames networking activity and affects innovative capability. The level of competitive pressure varies between markets, the potential for developing generalized technical solutions, dimensions of development and short-term vs. long-term investments. Therefore, it is not only the individual firms that determine which technical options are tested in the markets, but also non-market (quasi-market) mechanisms.

The technology being practised is assumed to be entrenched in knowledge, skills and manufactured goods, which are used by companies in a variety of ways along the value chain (Raffa 1992). Christensen and Munksgaard (2001), for example, split the value chain into three different activity phases: pre-production activities (e.g. research, development and design), production activities (e.g. process, maintenance and service) and a phase covering the activities related to the production follow-up (e.g. quality control, documentation, marketing and delivery). The first and the last phases are especially knowledge-intensive, whereas production activities are primarily regarded as technology-intensive. Following this distinction, the basic argument is that in order to become more knowledge-oriented, companies must also increasingly focus on pre-production and follow-up activities.

In a 'learning economy' countries will be able to create wealth in proportion to their capacity to learn and share innovation (Lundvall and Johnson 1994, Foray and Lundvall 1996). However, firms are limited by their own internal resources (knowledge, skills, experience, finance), and the internalization of all the required resources by small firms is not effective (Pyke and Sengenberger 1992). Therefore, further development means that the individual firm has to acquire external resources leading to the creation of new relationships. The overall resources of any firm include

internal resources, knowledge accumulated and learning capabilities, as well as the external resources that interaction with the environment creates (Corno *et al.* 1999). Collaboration in different networks, involving information-sharing and/or mutual learning (Johannisson *et al.* 2002), makes up for small size. Specialization and subcontracting involves sharing labour while enhancing the collective capacity and capability of the industrial district.

3.3.2 *Lessons from the field*

Most small firms in the region are subcontractors with larger customers, focusing mainly on the technology-intensive production phase and lacking their own sales force. 'Tell us what you need and we will make it', one CEO being interviewed states. So far, most firms have relied on producing goods with efficient machinery, but without a sufficient production control system to guide the actual manufacturing process. This has led to inefficient production, based mainly on gut feeling and experience. The demands of customers on the firms in the region are these days gradually becoming more focused on cost efficiency and flexibility. Increasing international competition calls for alternative ways to do business, e.g. investing in production technology and elaborating the relationships with customers.

The CEO of another of the companies visited confirms that with a reduced number of suppliers and customers there is a need for work collaboration, mainly in order to facilitate the flow of information. Additionally, the role of other industrial actors (e.g. trading companies) is increasing in the region. These players purchase goods from the most price-consistent producers, whether local or international. According to the CEO at the Industrial Development Centre, the local firms must therefore pro-actively approach new customers. However, still too many family businesses believe that things will work out without their changing their way of doing business. The major problem seems to be that firms in the region are too focused on just supplying a few multinationals (e.g. ABB, Electrolux, Ikea, Saab, Volvo, etc.).

The intensifying competition, the requirement for cost effectiveness and the increase of knowledge intensiveness are all underlying reasons for the diminishing returns from traditional means of local co-operation. The increasing number of (inter)national business owners in the region has also made the social life less important for conducting business. Instead of maintaining trust-enhancing personal contacts, the owner-managers should become more actively involved in formal co-operation with other regional firms. According to the CEO at the IDC, the local firms have little interest in investing in such collaboration. Furthermore, it takes a great deal to change from being a subcontractor to becoming a supplier of one's own products calling for continuous development. The IDC considers itself to be a significant networking agent in getting firms to come together to develop a 'bigger cake so that each of them will get a bigger piece'. The importance of production skills and export markets as well as of product development makes logistics, planning and efficient production techniques remain the core of the region, where in the future an increased

interaction between production and trading may well be expected. This way of business is already about to be enacted. A local ski company, which used to produce in Sweden at the time of the visit, now, two years later, produces in China while still designing and trading locally.

3.4 The industrial district as a federation

3.4.1 Conceptual overview

Limited human cognition calls for institutions that reduce uncertainty. Shared values mean that hierarchy originates in preferred norms rather than in status, that individualism and collectivism co-exist and that tradition is important. Frequent interaction created by and creating shared values and norms develops a trusting behaviour and builds the social capital needed to acquire supplementary resources. The importance of social capital for local development, for example, has been the subject of a growing number of studies in recent years (Coleman 1990, Flora 1998, Kilkenny *et al.* 1999, Westlund *et al.* 2002). Coleman (1990) relates social capital to the links between individuals/actors. He argues that most of the social capital can be viewed from a public-good perspective, i.e. it forms ‘an attribute of the social structure in which a person is embedded’ and that ‘social capital is not the private property of any of the persons who benefit from it’ (1990: 315). Following Coleman, Putnam (1993) extends the definition, applying it to societies and communities in general. Putnam’s interpretation of social capital has often been referred to as a ‘collective asset’ and a ‘common good’ of neighbourhoods and communities. However, Portes (1998), argues that social capital may have negative effects such as the exclusion of outsiders, excess claims on group members and restriction on individual freedom. The role of shared values in organizing economic activity comes through especially in the context of ethnic communities but applies in socially closed localities as well.

Figure 4. Shared values as the maker of the industrial district.

Social-capital theory provides a useful conceptual framework for understanding the embedded nature of ethnic business activity (Portes and Sensenbrenner 1993). Bonacich and Moedel (1980: 45) were the first to use the

concept of ethnic economy, which they define as ‘any ethnic or immigrant group’s self employed, employers, and their co-ethnic employees’. This specific economy force has become very important in some regions such as Miami, due to the Cuban ethnics, and New York, where many Chinese people reside (Fong *et al.* 2005). The new Americans often get established in specific sectors. Trust-building structures such as associations then play very important roles (Paxton 1999). Free churches, for example, because of the environment of brotherliness that is usually generated in such communities, trigger a trusting behaviour. On the one hand, the religion is a source of values such as hard work, and it can be a communication channel. On the other hand, the church can act as a basis for ‘social resourcing’ (Starr and MacMillan 1990) and even direct financing. You may borrow equipment and seek advice from owner-managers taking part in religious activities. Congregations as social arenas help with maintaining established relationships and building new ones to additional customers, for example. However, if only the original members of a community are trusted, it becomes a closed society creating a spirit that imposes a strong social control, which implies that sanctions are triggered if fundamental social values are violated. In this respect the Gnosjö-region is no exception (cf. Johannisson and Wigren 2006). These basic assumptions are summarized in the model in figure 4.

Religion, family and tradition jointly construct a shared value basis that guides firms as commercial agents. Shared values lead to trust, which in turn encourages co-competition, where creative tensions produce the energy needed to create a sustainable region. Immigration slowly contributes to diversity and the subsequent re-orientation of values, norms and practices that make the industrial district adapt to global change. Sustainability is also enforced by regional policies that promote education and subsequently open-mindedness.

3.4.2 *Lessons from the field*

Looking for what has made the businesses in the district successful and the area famous, the Gnosjö-spirit is usually referred to (cf. Johannisson 1984, Johannisson and Wigren 2006). This special atmosphere is mirrored in shared values, and its practice is reflected in intense informal communication and collaboration, individual and collective self-confidence, strong traditions in business creation and an everyday life characterized by hard work without extravagance. Shared values are enforced, as CEOs and their subordinates live next to each other and are in addition often closely related by kinship. Informal meetings are held on a regular basis, and sharing responsibilities in joint projection is a common practice. Additionally, informal agreements dominate business life which, according to the interviewed owner-managers, is characterized by personal relationships.

Sweden is an individualistic society (Hofstede 1980), but the Gnosjö-spirit confirms Tiessen’s (1997) argument that individualism and collectivism are not necessarily opposed. The individualism that the market calls for is absorbed by the well-known entrepreneurial spirit of the community where the shared values, business tradition, and team spirit point towards a collectivist behaviour. As

indicated, Johannisson (2000a, 2003) proposes that in the Gnosjö-region entrepreneurship should be associated with the industrial district as a collective. Besides, when problems appear, self-help is the spontaneous way of coping. For example, when the region's largest private employer, the German corporation Continental AG, closed down its plant at the turn of the millennium, 800 people were laid off. However, already within a year all but 50 persons were employed again (some had for certain moved out of the region).

In the Gnosjö-region business traditions come hand in hand with the Protestant ethic – a number of Free Churches are located there. These values promoting hard work are further enhanced by social associations such as Rotary and sport clubs but also by more general meeting-points such as the local restaurants. Formal associations and organizations (e.g. the trade unions and trade associations) also foster commitment to place.

When talking about the values in the area, one must consider the high portion of immigrants among the population. These new Swedes have actively contributed to the regional labour force and therefore they are locally much appreciated. From a superficial point of view, they also seem to be integrated into the community. Nevertheless, as pointed out by several of the interviewees as well as by, for example, Wigren (2003) and Johannisson and Wigren (2006), many problems remain below the surface. Many of the new Swedes choose to live in closed societies since a crucial condition for social integration is a good command of the Swedish language and submission to dominating local values. The fact that the businesses owned by immigrants with few exceptions are restaurants and other service businesses suggests that integration has not advanced very far in Gnosjö.

Another challenge is to keep up the tradition of a family business. Then, however, the new generation must share dominating norms and practices. After having got a taste of city life, many of the present owner-managers' children do not want to live in the region and are not very keen on working for 16 hours a day with no holidays (Davidsson 1995). According to its CEO, the IDC tackles the latter issue by proposing a change of the mentality from working 'more' to working 'smarter'. This smartness is needed for other reasons as well, such as increasingly global and competitive markets. The small firm that is robotizing its activities in order to compete with China demonstrates that the Gnosjö-industrial district is slowly becoming enlightened.

3.5 The industrial district as a networked community

3.5.1 Conceptual overview

Networking is generic to owner-managers. The need for independence makes them launch a business of their own, but once they have started the firm they realize their need for constant interaction with other agents on and beyond the market. Personal networking provides a way of organizing resources that is based on mutual trust and commitment (cf. Johannisson 2000a). Polenske (2004: 1034) states that if 'three or more firms collaborate or co-operate, they almost always create a formal or

informal network'. Five concepts provide a conceptual basis for looking upon the industrial district as a networked community: self-organizing, networking, knowledge transfer, family business and internationalization.

- (1) *Self-organizing*: Johannisson (2000a: 288) argues that a concept of self-organizing within an industrial district develops when 'autonomous units capable of multiple behavioural choices operate with individual freedom but clearly defined frames or references'. This implies that competition and co-operation co-exist, resulting in coherent sets or patterns in which neither hierarchy nor permanence reside, and in which information flows freely. When considering patterns of self-organizing in industrial districts and entrepreneurship, we should expect to find: (a) playfulness/ membership in local associations; (b) improvisation/flexibility in local business exchange; (c) commitment/local identity; and (d) social capability/community involvement.
- (2) *Networking*: According to Aldrich and Zimmer (1986: 14), a 'personal network perspective focuses on entrepreneurship as embedded in a social context, channelled and facilitated or constrained and inhibited by people's position in social networks'. When personal relations are created, parties volunteer to interact (Johannisson 2000b). Owing to the mutuality of such ties, once they are established, they, however, create (inter)dependence (Mackinnon *et al.* 2004, Polenske 2004). According to Pyke and Sengenberger (1992), industrial districts are able to take advantage of their proximity to start tight and extensive networks. Geographical proximity improves effectiveness by
 - (i) diffusing ideas and technical innovation; (ii) inviting to various kinds of collaboration between firms and of a broader political kind; (iii) building social cohesion and a sense of collective consciousness; and (iv) facilitating and speeding up inter-firm transactions.
- (3) *Knowledge transfer*: Industrial districts facilitate virtuous self-enforcing processes of collective learning because (a) they are repositories of tacit and idiosyncratic knowledge embedded in local firms and institutions (Maskell and Malmberg 1999, Giuliani 2003), (b) firms are interlinked in local production chains and are socially embedded, which leads them to interact, exchange information and foster joint innovation. According to Aasheim (1994), this is both because industrial districts support the adoption, adaptation and diffusion of innovation among SMEs and because the process of incremental creation of knowledge is acknowledged (see also Harding and Pauer 2001).
- (4) *Family business*: Sharma *et al.* (1997: 2) state that the *family-owned business* is 'a business governed and/or managed on a sustainable, potentially cross-generational, basis to shape and perhaps pursue the formal or implicit vision of the business held by members of the same family or small number of families'. The new generation is challenged by extending the entrepreneur's range of contacts (Cromie 1994) introducing new business associates (Birley 1985) and offering

motivation, support and encouragement (Johannisson 2000a).

Figure 5. A networked model of the sustainable industrial district.

- (5) *Internationalization*: The lack of resources, general uncertainty and the complexity of the process usually work against small firms' involvement in foreign expansion. Hence, theories emphasize networking for learning and experience-sharing on the market and present them as a crucial resource for initiating and maintaining the internationalization process (cf. Erikson *et al.* 1997).

In synthesis, the proposed networked model starts with the principle of self-organizing, which denotes a voluntary and shared ambition among the firms in the region to come together and create a functioning framework, in which they may network and collaborate, where trust, as it evolves over time, appears as a binding element (figure 5). This shared insight makes the founders develop the skills of their potential successors, and also makes them benefit from established external trust relationships. Considering the globalized (business) world, it becomes especially important to integrate international ties with local ones.

3.5.2 *Lessons from the field*

The densely-knit personal relations between the owner-managers within the Gnosjö industrial district make it into a self-organized unit. All interviewees mentioned the strong sense of belonging, fed by the spontaneous voluntary exchange of both resources and information. The sharing of ideas and emerging business opportunities appear as established practices in the Gnosjö region, where many business leaders also engage in joint agreements. One of the interlocutors stated that the resourceful networks within the community are of crucial importance to the viability of individual firms.

Thus, there seems to be no need for outside agents such as the Industrial Development Centre to mediate in order to enforce collaboration between the entrepreneurs. The field report rather confirms that the entrepreneurs prefer to establish contacts on their own initiative. All the interviewed actors stated, either

explicitly or implicitly, that trust was crucial for the business activities in the area. This, for example, means that local suppliers are only changed if they do not meet productivity requirements; because of constant interaction between the business partners, flexible arrangements that are confirmed with a handshake can easily be made. These close relationships make companies in the Gnosjö-area ready to support each other in case of an emergency. Only a phone call to a neighbour is needed. Basic formal institutions in the region also enforce trust between the members of the business community. The school, for example, offers an arena for general exchange, besides providing tailor-made further education.

As indicated, many family businesses in the Gnosjö-industrial district are on the brink of undergoing succession. Several interviewees stated that the family businesses rely heavily on networking and mutual trust accumulated from generation to generation. Being brought up locally within the Gnosjö-community spirit, one of the business owners being interviewed revealed that not only had he been mentored in the business by his father but also he had inherited networking practices and trustful contacts.

Today the main efforts as regards growth and expansion concern international contacts and exposure. Networking plays a key role in finding the initial foreign contact, often by locally finding 'someone who knows someone'. Once the relationship with the foreign partners has been established, personal interaction and trust-building begin. Possibly because of their own fin-spun local networking, the Gnosjö owner-managers pay special attention to the culture of their foreign partners and respect their way of doing business.

In essence, companies in a networked community such as the Gnosjö-region enhance their business activities both inside and outside the region through an elaborate network of trust relationships. It is because of spontaneous collaboration within the business community that the Gnosjö-region has so far been able to cope with market and social challenges and therefore still remains an inspiration for other localities in Sweden.

4. Interstanding as a learning experience for researchers and reflective practitioners

Inquiring into the industrial-district phenomenon, the four ways of modelling an industrial district in a Swedish context all seem to be able to make sense out of an encountered 'real' world. The approaches appear to be equally conceptually and empirically justified. What else is to be expected? If four blind (wo)men touch an elephant they will vividly characterize the animal in a way that makes their sensory impressions become comprehensible and fit their earlier experiences. If four groups of young researchers are given different maps and approach an ambiguous social setting of an industrial district, they will surely ascribe different features to it, according to the directions the map provides. The conclusion of this exercise reflects basic ontological assumptions. Those who practice an objectivist approach will argue that this outcome signals the need for a more complex conceptual framework to re-

present the ‘real’ truth. (Social) constructionists will, in contrast, just lean back and happily state that their generic argument has been confirmed – that any image of reality, also that which is constructed by researchers, is the outcome of local negotiations. Using Morgan’s (1980) language, the four theoretical frameworks appear as different metaphors and the adopted methodology as ‘puzzle-solving’. Theories provide images of reality that make sense and inspire field research, and methodologies help with fitting the sensory impressions in the field into the proposed overall image of reality. Thus, it is up to the reader to decide whether the lessons from the research reported here should be used as a starting-point for the making of an integrated framework or be seen as the insight that ‘interstanding’ is an everlasting effort that every researcher has to accept. There are, of course, yet other ways of gaining insight than intentionally juxtaposing existing conceptual frameworks. Staying within the objectivist paradigm, Eisenhardt (1989), as indicated above, proposes a dialogue between conceptualizing efforts and field experiences as a way of generating new theory. Narrative approaches founded in the field itself invite themselves if a social-constructionist paradigm is adopted.

The learning context created by the group exercise was not just an intellectual challenge. It gained momentum by also genuinely affecting the students. Joint conceptualization by a group of researchers seems to energize, if there is, as in this case, a competition between different embodied images of reality. The strong emotional commitment that each student team evoked during the different phases of the assignment – while preparing it, when visiting the field and there competing about the time and attention of the interlocutors and, finally, when promoting their case at the final seminar – amplified their alertness as model-makers, conversation-creators and observers/account-constructors in the field. Once the students’ need had been met for unlearning the ‘trained incapacity’ to face and cope with contrasting views which they had experienced in their previous formal education, intra-group sense-making processes accelerated. Only on the second day of the field research did the doctoral students fully realize that teamwork and intense interaction with the persons they encountered in the industrial district were needed in order to create, justify and actively defend ‘their’ theory, their own construction of reality.

Our proposed model of academic quality – the very interrelations between research, education and community dialogue, cf. figure 1 – can be used to reflect upon the dynamic learning context that the course created. In order to energize this exercise the particular conceptual and methodological lessons made in 2005 will be supported by, on the one hand, the senior researcher’s experiences from organizing the course annually over more than a decade, and by his more than three decades of intermittent research in the Gnosjö industrial district, on the other. As the model promises, the educational (ad)venture as a potential for increased exchange between the academic and business communities will also be elaborated upon.

We began with the interface between research and education. In the doctoral course wherein this paper originates, theoretical ideas which reached far beyond those addressed in the field assignment were discussed and used as a shared conceptual platform. The student teams also made good use of their freedom to organize and

carry out both the conceptual framing and the empirical exercise within the allocated model. The students' emotional commitment, for certain energized by both inter-group and intra-group tensions, albeit not always constructive, focused and sharpened the students' analyses. Mutual learning was further enforced by intentionally making the groups diverse with respect to academic and practical experience, cultural background and gender. At the same time, the small size of the groups (three doctoral students in each) facilitated the intra-group organizing of the task.

Continuing with the bridge between education and community dialogue, the design of the course produced several modes of learning. The very visits by the students and their 'interrogation' from different angles presumably gave the owner-managers and other practitioners an opportunity to reflect upon their practices. The mere fact that the region was visited by international junior researchers, forcing the local entrepreneurs to use a foreign language when explaining their operations, invited reflection on the local ways of doing business and relating to a globalizing world. Previous research states that the Gnosjö region and its business community are trapped in their own historical successes and the thereby its associated unreflecting self-righteousness. Experiences from new encounters of different kinds may facilitate a break-out and accumulate into a new and viable collective identity (Johannisson and Wigren 2006).

The challenge is obviously to bring academic knowledge and perspectives to actors in the district, while adopting an interactive mode. Optional tactics to make the different stakeholders in the industrial district share the outcome of the whole course exercise include inviting them to the final course seminar at the university, organizing a seminar in the district itself and delivering written reports in an 'everyday language' to the interviewees. However, since the student groups are international and the language, accordingly, English, neither of these measures is feasible. The course leader may of course summarize the findings in his native tongue (Swedish) and then bring them to the practitioners. But then the dynamics and evocative power of the contrasting reports and the dramatized university seminar would vanish. Instead alternative ways of communicating spontaneously emerged during the site visits. While carrying out the planned enquiry, the students created frequent opportunities for informal conversations with the practitioners. Since some of the student co-authors have a family business background, these encounters in some cases emerged into quite intense dialogues.

It would be too pretentious to expect that the students, with just two days of field experiences in the Gnosjö industrial district, should be able to provide normative recommendations for change in the local business community. However, the senior author, who has repeatedly visited the region over the last three decades, has presumably gained the insight, the legitimacy and even the responsibility to intervene. As early as the 1980s he was recognized as a concerned but critical voice in the region, a position he had gained. In the mid-1990s, in the context of that year's course, he used that position to create a spectacular bridge between research and the (business) community, the third interface according to figure 1. He then condensed and 'translated' the two contrasting views 'Corporation' and 'Networked

community', according to the reports by that year's international students, into two newspaper articles which – obviously! – provided contradictory messages. One of the articles thus proposed that the industrial district should be considered as a role model for any localized business-development effort in Sweden, paying attention to the importance of social capital and collective tacit knowledge. The other article delivered the message that the days of the industrial district were numbered due to the shortage of formally trained management. The two articles were published on the very same day in two different regional newspapers. The intention of this set-up was to create an awareness that the Gnosjö industrial district was as vulnerable as any locality in a globalized world.

Although a third article was published a week later, where the purpose of the set-up was clarified, the many owner-managers in the district only read the negative article. An intense debate took off in the region, and 3 months after the articles were published the senior author had to defend his view at a public meeting, attracting about 200 owner-managers and lasting for several hours. These events left a surge that remained for several years in the region, possibly contributing to the creation of an industrial development centre (cf. Johannisson 2000). This 'provocative' interactive research questioned what had been taken for granted in the region, and what so far had generated success, but where changing global conditions presumably called for change in local practices. Provocative research both resembles and differs from what is usually associated with critical enquiry. 'Critical research generally aims at disrupting ongoing social reality for the sake of providing impulses to the liberation from or resistance to what dominates and leads to constraints in human decision making' (Alvesson and Deetz 2000: 1). In order to break through the thick layer of self-sufficiency, as the one embedding the Gnosjö industrial district, the responsible researcher may have to use dramatized hands-on measures, as the enacted debate, to create crisis awareness. Just an intellectual enquiry disseminated in traditional academic channels will not do.

5. Inspiration for research, implications for policy

The posthumous reputation of the late Swedish film director Ingmar Bergman presents him as a man of great visions and integrity but also as a good listener. As indicated, the creation of the learning experience that the field research reported here calls for a teacher with a sharp ear and with associated curiosity and concern for his or her own learning. Even if different theoretical lenses produce varying impressions and understandings of a phenomenon such as the constitution of an industrial district, further enquiry may make them intertwine into an even richer story, which rather builds on the very relationships between individual images than on the images themselves. Again borrowing from the world of moviemaking, the American film director Robert Altman in his movie 'Shortcuts' visualizes how different life stories by coincidence intertwine, thereby leaving a much richer imprint of urban life than stories just brought together as a bundle. Along a similar vein, by forcing the students to adopt different conceptual images on the industrial-

district phenomenon being researched, they were made aware of the complexity of social life rather than given a definitive answer to its constitution. This triggers further research, where the interfaces between the four conceptual models being tested (here) with respect to their potentiality as regards making sense of the industrial-district phenomenon provide substantial inspiration. Our own research in the Gnosjö region since the European Doctoral Programme began its visits includes several reports (e.g. Johannisson 2000, Johannisson and Wigren 2006).

As much as the analytical enquiry into the industrial district phenomenon varies according to proposed models, the practical implications in terms of measures aiming at enforcing favourable processes and stopping disadvantageous ones at an early stage should differ between the conceptual frames as well. However, for various reasons public-policy measures based on each model may not appear as distinct as their analytical origin. First, the models are abstract and simplified constructs, which are regulated by a number of analytical contingencies in order to point out critical characteristics. It goes without saying that when these academic products are put into the hands of practitioners, contextual adaptation must take place. Reality as a multi-faceted practice that invites different interpretations then hits back. Second, a number of those contextual contingencies that have to be considered will probably concern issues that are brought up by one or several of the (three) optional models. Third, even if each model provides different explanations for the (eroding) sustainability of an industrial district, not all the coping measures needed are suited for policy intervention on different societal levels. Fourth, keeping the image of 'crystallization' in mind, the four conceptual models, individually and jointly, only represent analytical means of making some sense of a phenomenon that is ultimately local and thus beyond conclusive conceptualization and generalization.

Thus, there is neither a good reason, nor any large space for interpreting ongoing changes in the Gnosjö industrial district or outlining detailed (public-policy) programmes based on each model. However, obviously, the corporation model acknowledges the insidious concentrations to larger units, often caused by succession problems and globalizing markets. The network/technology system view is partially enacted through the creation of the Industrial Development Centre and the different regionalized public technology programmes that it administers. The federation model indicates a need for integrating the different value systems that today separate, on one hand, the local family businesses and the externally controlled business units, and on the other, the local people with roots going generations back and the new community members from other parts of Sweden and abroad. Some cultural activities, such as a local theatre plays, have also tried to build much needed bridges. The networked-community model, finally, acknowledging the differences between different groups and individuals with respect to values and practices, is reflected in a healthy scepticism as regards new trends. There is also an ongoing polylogue on these issues involving many stakeholders. It goes without saying that such processes are difficult to govern by way of public policy. Yet each model provides a point of departure for reflections concerning public policy as well as for self-reflexivity in the region.

Staging and producing interstanding and the mentorship of young researchers

A commentary by Angelo Bisignano, Nottingham Trent University

As a young (please read inexperienced) researcher, I was (I am) eager for ‘truth’ and ‘results’. I would like to be ‘the discoverer’ of something no one else has seen before, and I would like to be ‘the innovator’ of solutions that can give answers to those challenging Knowledge through academia. Wherever I look, however, it seems that I am trapped between conflicting extremes. On the one hand, my formation inside an ‘objectivistic’ paradigmatic approach offers me the possibility to create ‘models’ that can be generalized and that I can propose as correct answers to problems or strategic choices. On the other hand, the fieldwork presents me with the peculiarities of each business story: local conditions, contextual situations, personal stories show the thread of my ‘models’. Moreover, my doctoral programme is designed, on the basis of a national intellectual tradition, for deductive research and the academics evaluating my work expect a clear deductive structure telling what I ‘found’. Contemporarily, the temptation to practise reflexivity is frustrated by (my) inexperience in both handling and presenting such complex methodological approaches and by the lack of academic legitimacy that such work requires.

The notion of interstanding takes an inexperienced researcher like me beyond the dichotomies characterizing the dilemmatic early days in the academic arena. The meta-methodology created helps the inexperienced researcher in several ways.

First, producing interstanding creates an awareness of the complexity of the phenomenon observed. The simplification of reality(ies) through models can seduce the inexperienced researcher, reducing the attention to ‘localization’ that even the most sophisticated model requires in order to explain contextual peculiarities. Although crystallization can offer a taste of the polyedric nature of social phenomena, it always has a focus centred on a specific point of view. Interstanding, on the other hand, allows us to hear different voices and to confront them.

Second, staging and producing ‘interstanding’, the researcher develops a consciousness of the need of a continuous dialogical interaction with the community(ies) he/she interfaces with. The Vařjõ experiment suggested how the students exposed to multiple dialogues developed an attention to the exchange of ideas and understandings with the business community and reflected together with owners-managers upon their practices. Moreover, the students made sense of the meaning(s) of the industrial district in the Gnosjo”area dialoguing with researchers that have been studying the phenomenon over a decade and with their educators in the context of the doctoral course. These students therefore developed a prospective attention to generate ‘holistic’ insights of complex phenomena and to bridge and transfer knowledge between communities.

Third, the (inexperienced) researcher has the opportunity to gain experience maintaining a focus on the learning process. Academic quality, described as interrelation between research, education and community dialogue, needs to be enhanced by continuous learning. In the experiment the students not only produced new insights on the Gnosjö industrial district through a ‘staged polylogue’, but, more importantly, they learnt how to (co)create data and understandings with a community studied and with the academic community of reference.

Fourth, understanding such a meta-methodological approach, the inexperienced researcher develops a critical way of (re)thinking and (re)evaluating his/her own research. Producing interstanding, in fact, offers space for a conceptual variety that would be otherwise limited by the traditional loneliness of the researcher. Even in research teams, the assumption of a specific methodological stand confines the understanding to a single perspective. The students in the Växjö experiment, instead, developed a unique capability of self-assessment and critical view.

The Växjö experiment’ showed how the polylogue required for interstanding social phenomena enhances an interactive bridging between education, research, and community dialogue. Contemporarily, it unveils a world of possibilities and challenges not only for inexperienced researchers, but also for all the different communities involved in the academic dialogue(s). The reflection in the business community upon practices and behaviour, for instance, gains dynamism and can improve the sensemaking and sensegiving of crucial activities and behaviours. Interstanding social phenomena ultimately calls for a revisiting of the internal relationships characterizing each dimension of the academic work. So, the relationship mentor– mentee (senior researcher–student) in education assumes innovative nuances with the mentor that becomes a ‘moderator’ of the rival viewpoints and through dialogue with the mentees favours a ‘guided experimentation’ of the interaction across boundaries.

Acknowledgement

We want to thank Poul Rind Christensen, not only for his contributions as a teacher on the course ‘SMEs in Economic and Regional Development’ for more than a decade, but also for his very constructive comments on an earlier version of this paper.

Notes

1. Adopting a linguistic turn Hjorth (2001) uses the notion of 'interstanding' in a slightly different way, meaning that the (individual) researcher gains insight by relating to different (existing) texts.
2. When the first/senior author of this paper was invited to expand on the notion of the 'Gnosjo' spirit' for the Swedish National Encyclopedia he invited a reflecting practitioner, the local historian and former planning officer at the municipality, to jointly provide a description.
3. I am grateful to Poul Rind Christensen for suggesting the kaleidoscope metaphor in this context.
4. In order to keep comparability over the years (the assignment originally was implemented in 1993) some references used as basic conceptual input have been kept ever since. Today they may seem to be a bit outdated.
5. Since every researcher, the senior author being no exception, has a pre-understanding of a phenomenon this introduction to the alternative understandings of the industrial district can not provide an 'objective' platform for the messages of the following sections. However, the 'fact' that the senior researcher has spent three decades studying the Gnosjo industrial districts makes him the most appropriate introducer to the field.

References

- Aasheim, B. T. 1994 Industrial districts, inter-firm co-operation and endogenous technological development: the experience of developed countries, in *Technological Dynamism in Industrial Districts: An Alternative Approach to Industrialization in Developing Countries?* (New York & Geneva: UNCTAD and UN) pp. 91–142.
- Aldrich, H. E. and Zimmer, C. 1986 Entrepreneurship through social networks, in Aldrich, H. E. (ed.), *Population Perspectives on Organizations* (Uppsala: Acta Universitatis Upsaliensis) pp. 13–28.
- Allison, G. T. 1971 *Essence of Decisionmaking. Explaining the Cuban Missile Crisis* (Boston: Little Brown).
- Alvesson, M. and Deetz, S. 2000 *Doing Critical Management Research* (London: Sage).
- Alvesson, M. and Skoldberg, K. 2000 *Reflexive Methodology. New Vistas for Qualitative Research* (London: Sage).
- Becattini, G. 1990 The Marshallian industrial district as a socio-economic notion, in Pyke, F., Becattini, G. and Sengenberger, W. (eds), *Industrial Districts and Inter-firm Cooperation in Italy* (Geneva: ILU) pp. 37–51.
- Birley, S. 1985 The role of networks in the entrepreneurial process, *Journal of Business Venturing*, 1: 107–117.
- Bjuggren, P. and Sund, L. 2002 A transaction cost rationale for transition of the firm within the family, *Small Business Economics*, 19: 123–133.
- Blomqvist, K., Kylaheiko, K. and Virolainen, V. M. 2002 Filling a gap in traditional transaction cost economics: towards transaction benefits-based analysis, *International Journal of Production Economics*, 79: 1–14.
- Bonach, E. and Model, J. 1980 *The Economic Basis of Ethnic Solidarity* (Berkeley & Los Angeles, CA: University of California Press).
- Burrell, G. and Morgan, G. 1988 [1979] *Sociological Paradigms and Organizational Analysis* (Aldershot: Gower).
- Carlsson, B. and Stankiewicz, R. 1991 On the nature, function, and composition of technological systems, *Journal of Evolutionary Economics*, 1: 93–118.
- Christensen, P. R. and Munksgaard, K. B. 2001 Transformationspres og inerti I en klynge af sma' virksomheder, *Nordiske Organisasjonsstudier*, 3: 82–109.
- Coase, R. H. 1937 The nature of the firm, *Economica (New Series)*, 4: 386–405.
- Coleman, J. S. 1990 *Foundations of Social Theory* (Cambridge, MA: Harvard Business Press).
- Corno, F., Reinmoeller, P. and Nonaka, I. 1999 Knowledge creation within industrial systems, *Journal of Management and Governance*, 3: 379–394.
- Cromie, S. 1994 Entrepreneurship: the role of the individual in small business development, *IBAR*, 5: 62–75.
- Davidsson, P. 1995 Culture, structure and regional levels of entrepreneurship, *Entrepreneurship and Regional Development*, 7: 41–62.
- Denzin, N. K. 1978 *The Research Act: A Theoretical Introduction to Sociological Methods*, 2nd edn (New York: McGraw-Hill).
- Eisenhardt, K. M. 1989 Building theories from case study research, *Academy of Management Review*, 14: 532–550.
- Eriksson, K., Johanson, J., Majkgard, A. and Sharma, D. 1997 Experiential knowledge and cost in the internationalization process, *Journal of International Business Studies*, 28: 337–360.
- Etzkowitz, H. and Leydesdorff, L. (eds) 1997 *Universities and the Global Knowledge Economy* (London: Pinter).
- Flora, J. L. 1998 Social capital and communities of place, *Rural Sociology*, 63: 481–506.
- Fong, E., Luk, C. and Ooka, E. 2005 Spatial distribution of suburban ethnic business, *Social Science Research*, 34: 215–235.

- Foray, D. and Lundvall, B.-A. 1996 The knowledge-based economy: from the economics of knowledge to the learning economy, in *Employment and Growth in the Knowledge-Based Economy* (Paris: OECD).
- Giuliani, E. 2003 Knowledge in the air and its uneven distribution: a story of a Chilean wine cluster, paper presented at the DRUID Winter conference, Aalborg.
- Giuliani, E. 2007 The selective nature of knowledge networks in clusters: evidence from the wine industry. *Journal of Economic Geography*, 7: 139–168.
- Håkansson, H. 1987 (ed.) *Industrial Technological Development: A Network Approach* (London: Croom-Helm).
- Harding, S. and Pawer, K. S. 2001 Know-how share and transfer in SME networks: a contingent approach, paper presented at the 7th International Conference on Concurrent Enterprizing, Bremen.
- Hjorth, D. 2001 *Rewriting Entrepreneurship. Enterprise Discourse and Entrepreneurship in the Case of RE-organising ES*. Doctoral thesis. Acta Vexionensia, No 13/2001. Business Administration (Vaxjö: Vaxjö University Press).
- Hjorth, D. and Steyaert, C. 2004 (eds) *Narrative and Discursive Approaches in Entrepreneurship* (Cheltenham: Edward Elgar).
- Hofstede, G. 1980 *Culture's Consequences: International Differences in Work-Related Values* (Beverly Hills, CA: Sage).
- Janesick, V. J. 2000 The choreography of qualitative research design, in Denzin, N. K. and Lincoln, Y. S. (eds), *Handbook of Qualitative Research*, 2nd edn (London: Sage) pp. 379–399.
- Jick, T. D. 1979 Mixing qualitative and quantitative methods: triangulation action, *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 24: 602–611.
- Johannisson, B. 1983 Swedish evidence for the potential of local entrepreneurship in regional development, *European Small Business Journal*, 1: 11–24.
- Johannisson, B. 1984 A cultural perspective on small business – local business climate. *International Small Business Journal*, 2(2): 32–43.
- Johannisson, B. 2000a Modernizing the industrial district: rejuvenating or managerial colonization?, in Vatne, E. and Taylor, M. (eds), *The Networked Firm in a Global World: Small Firms in New Environments* (Aldershot: Ashgate) pp. 283–307.
- Johannisson, B. 2000b Networking and entrepreneurial growth, in Sexton, D. and Landström, H. (eds), *Handbook of Entrepreneurship* (London: Blackwell) pp. 368–386.
- Johannisson, B. 2003 Entrepreneurship as a collective phenomenon. In Genesca, E., Urbano, D., Capelleras, J., Gualarte, C. and Verge, J. (eds) *Creació'n de Empreses – Entrepreneurship* (Barcelona, Spain: Servei de Publicacions de la Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona), pp. 87–109.
- Johannisson, B. and Wigren, C. 2006 The dynamics of community identity making – the Spirit of Gnosjö revisited, in Steyaert, C. and Hjorth, D. (eds), *Entrepreneurship as Social Change* (Cheltenham: Edward Elgar) pp. 188–209.
- Johannisson, B., Ramírez-Pasillas, M. and Karlsson, G. 2002 The institutional embeddedness of local inter-firm networks: a leverage for business creation, *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development*, 14: 297–315.
- Johannisson, B., Nowicki, K., Alexanderson, O. and Senneseth, K. 1994 Beyond anarchy and organization: entrepreneurs in contextual networks, *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development*, 6: 329–356.
- Johansson, A. W. 1999 How can consultants advise SMEs?, in Johannisson, B. and Landström, H. (eds), *Images of Entrepreneurship and Small Business* (Lund/Vaxjö/Örebro: Studentlitteratur/SIRE/FSF) pp. 141–164.
- Karlsson, C. and Larsson, J. 1993 A macro-view of the Gnosjö entrepreneurial spirit, *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development*, 5: 117–140.
- Kilkenny, M., Nalbarte, L. and Besser, T. 1999 Reciprocated community support and small town–small business success, *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development*, 11: 231–246.
- Larsson, R. 1993 Case survey methodology: quantitative analysis of patterns across case studies, *Academy of Management Journal*, 35: 1515–1546.
- Lundvall, B. A. and Johnson, S. 1994 The learning economy, *Journal of Industry Studies*, 1: 23–42.
- Mackinnon, D., Chapman, K. and Cumbers, A. 2004 Networking, trust and embeddedness amongst SMEs in the Aberdeen oil complex, *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development*, 16: 87–106.
- Marshall, A. 1920 [1890] *Principles of Economics*, 8th edn (London: Macmillan).
- Martin, R. and Sunley, P. 2003 Deconstructing clusters: chaotic concept or policy panacea? *Journal of Economic Geography*, 3: 5–35.
- Maskell, P. and Malmberg, A. 1999 Localized learning and industrial competitiveness, *Cambridge Journal of Economics*, 23: 167–185.
- Maskell, P., Eskelinen, H., Hannibalsson, I., Malmberg, A. and Vatne, E. 1998 *Competitiveness, Localized Learning and Regional Development* (London: Routledge).
- Morgan, G. 1980 Paradigms, metaphors and puzzle solving in organization theory, *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 25: 605–622.
- Morgan, G. 2006 *Images of Organization* (London: Sage).
- Nooteboom, B. 1993 Firm size effects on transaction costs, *Small Business Economics*, 4: 283–295.

- Paxton, P. 1999 Is social capital declining in the United States? A multiple indicator assessment, *American Journal of Sociology*, 105: 88–127.
- Pettersson, K. 2004 Masculine entrepreneurship – the Gnosjö-discourse in a feminist perspective, in Hjorth, D. and Steyaert, C. (eds), *Narrative and Discursive Approaches in Entrepreneurship* (Cheltenham: Edward Elgar) pp. 177–193.
- Polenske, K. 2004 Competition, collaboration and co-operation: an uneasy triangle in networks of firms and regions, *Regional Studies*, 38: 1029–1043.
- Porter, M. 1990 The competitive advantage of nations, *Harvard Business Review*, March–April: 73–93.
- Portes, A. 1998 Social capital: its origins and applications in modern sociology, *Annual Review of Sociology*, 24: 1–24.
- Portes, A. and Sensenbrenner, J. 1993 Embeddedness and immigration: notes on the social determinants of economic action, *American Journal of Sociology*, 98: 1320–1350.
- Putnam, R. D. 1993 The prosperous community. Social capital and public life, *The American Prospect*, 13: 35–42.
- Pye, F. and Sengenberger, W. 1992 *Industrial Districts and Local Economic Regeneration* (Geneva: International Institute for Labour Studies).
- Rabellotti, G. 1997 *External Economies and Cooperation in Industrial Districts; A Comparison of Italy and Mexico* (Basingstoke: Macmillan).
- Raffa, M. 1992 A relationships typology in firms networks. Unpublished conference paper, 8th IMP Conference, Lyon.
- Richardson, L. 1994 Writing. A method of inquiry, in Denzin, N. K. and Lincoln, S. (eds), *Handbook of Qualitative Research* (London: Sage) pp. 516–529.
- Schmitz, H. 1995 Collective efficiency: growth path for small-scale industry, *Journal of Development Studies*, 31: 529–566.
- Sharma, P., Chrisman, J. J. and Chua, J. H. 1997 Strategic management of the family business: past research and future challenges, *Family Business Review*, 10: 1–35.
- Sjöstrand, S. E. 1992 On the rationale behind irrational institutions, *Journal of Economic Issues*, 26: 1007–1040.
- Starr, J. R. and MacMillan, I. C. 1990 Resource cooptation via social contracting: resource acquisition strategies for new ventures, *Strategic Management Journal*, Special Issue, Summer, 11: 79–92.
- Teece, D. J. 2000 *Managing Intellectual Capital: Organizational, Strategic, and Policy Dimensions* (New York: Oxford University Press).
- Tiessen, J. H. 1997 Individualism, collectivism, and entrepreneurship: a framework for international comparative research, *Journal of Business Venturing*, 12: 367–384.
- Wenger, E. 1998 *Communities of Practice. Learning, Meaning and Identity* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press).
- Westlund, H., Forsberg, A. and Höckertin, C. 2002 Social capital and local development in Swedish rural districts, paper prepared for the 42nd Congress of the European Science Association, Dortmund, Germany, 27–31 August.
- Wigren, C. 2003 *The Spirit of Gnosjö. The Grand Narrative and Beyond*. PhD thesis (Jönköping: Jönköping International Business School).
- Williamson, O. E. 1975 *Markets and Hierarchies: Analysis and Antitrust Implications* (New York: The Free Press).
- Williamson, O. E. 1979 Transaction-cost economics: the governance of contractual relations, *Journal of Law and Economics*, 22: 233–261.
- Williamson, O. E. 1985 *The Economic Institutions of Capitalism; Firms, Markets, Relational Contracting* (New York: The Free Press).
- Yin, R. K. 1994 *Case Study Research: Design and Methods* (Newbury Park, CA: Sage).